

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF PROCESSING SHAPED SURFACES WITH CARBIDE CUTTERS

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Abstract: *The article discusses ways to improve the performance of carbide cutters on shaped surfaces, as well as used cutters for processing shaped surfaces.*

Key Words: *Shaped surfaces, models, process, processing, technology.*

The main part

Creating an effective model of the curved surface processing process is quite a difficult task due to the complexity and variable nature of the processes occurring in the processing zone. But despite such factors, the actuality of the topic has not changed its direction in the study of this issue.

Mechanical processing of shaped surfaces is rather difficult and is provided by complex kinematics of the movement of the cutting tool relative to the workpiece being processed, and is also characterized by variable values of technological factors that determine the processing conditions.

Since the details of complex shape, having shaped surfaces, require careful consideration and improvement taking into account current trends, consider a review of research and development. Modern computer systems of high-performance equipment exclude the possibility of automatic assignment of cutting modes by the system itself. The system takes into account the current state of the workpiece, which allows you to optimize the control program for processing modes in order to speed up the process, increase the efficiency of equipment use and improve the quality of processing. In this case, the tool path is divided into elementary sections with a given step.

Comparing the volume of the material being removed at each site with the recommended specified cutting conditions, the system assigns the optimal feed at each site. Although the system calculates the optimal feed values automatically, nevertheless, the initial parameters for certain processing conditions are set by the technologist based on his own experience or according to the tables of cutting modes provided by the tool supplier.

However, these comparisons of determining optimal cutting modes do not take into account the variability of the processing parameters of shaped surfaces, which requires their further development.

A review of literature sources has shown that not all automatic control systems are built according to an optimization algorithm, but systems. the design of control programs for CNC machines are not able to design the optimal technology or take into account only the geometric conditions of forming the surface of the part. In addition, current trends in the development of software products show that their improvement is taking place in the direction of optimizing the cutting process and the entire technological processing system when designing control programs for CNC machines.

It is known that for any cutting process, the geometric parameters of the allowance layer determine the process as a whole. These parameters depend on the shape of the workpiece, the actual shape of the tool surface and the actual trajectory of the shaping movement, which determines the relative position of the tool and the workpiece during processing. As a result of geometric interaction with the removal of the allowance, the treated surface is formed, as well as its macro and microgeometry. The most complex processes occur during the formation of the physical and mechanical properties of the surface layer (roughness, the nature and magnitude of residual stresses, structural transformations). At the same time, the process of processing the shaped surface is characterized by a constant change in the parameters of the cutting process, which necessitates a detailed study of their mutual

influence, establishing relationships and patterns of their influence on the processes in the cutting zone.

Modern research reflected in the work of Professor M.L. Heifetz has shown that combined processing methods are the most effective. For various reasons, the scope of use of many effective processes is significantly limited, in such cases, combining them with another method can achieve a given state of the surface layer and expand technological capabilities.

Details of complex shape having shaped surfaces have become widespread, therefore, the technological processes of their manufacture, which have some features, require careful consideration and improvement taking into account modern trends. The existing traditional technological processes of processing shaped surfaces, considered in the works of E.G. Granovsky, A.M. Dalsky, I.A. Druzhinsky, V.P. Firago, P.I. Lizarditsyn, etc., are reduced to the use of one of two main methods:

1. A shaped cutting tool (cutter, broach, milling cutter, countersink, grinding wheel), the shape of the cutting edge of which corresponds to the shape of the shaped surface being processed and copies it;
2. A simple cutting tool (cutter, milling cutter, grinding wheel), the cutting blade of which is in point or linear contact with the shaped surface being processed.

Figure 1 – Processing of a shaft with shaped surfaces (animation: 16 frames, 4 repetition cycles, 215 kilobytes).

Obviously, the first processing method is more productive, but less economical due to the need to design and manufacture a special cutting tool. In addition, the

possibility of using a shaped cutting tool directly depends on the size and shape of the surface being processed. In the second case, the formation of a shaped surface is provided by the kinematics of the processing process, which informs the tool of the corresponding curvilinear motion relative to the workpiece being processed, which is ensured by the use of copying systems or numerical control machines (CNC), which has already been mentioned.

Currently, methods for optimizing cutting processes according to the criteria of maximum productivity or minimum cost are well developed, however, these methods for determining optimal cutting modes do not take into account the variability of the processing parameters of shaped surfaces, which requires their further development.

However, it should be noted that in order to solve the problem of ensuring the accuracy of processing, the authors have carried out studies for cylindrical surfaces and do not take into account the features of processing parts with a shaped profile. In the works devoted to the processing of shaped surfaces, the solution of this problem is determined by the assignment of variable operating conditions of processing using techniques that take into account only one or several variable parameters. In order to effectively manage the processing process in this case, it is advisable to perform on the basis of techniques that take into account the entire complex of process variables and their relationship.

The quality of products is understood as a set of properties to the extent of the usefulness of products that meet certain social and personal needs in accordance with its purpose. Quality improvement is an important condition for increasing production efficiency.

Information on the justification of the choice of optimal cutting modes, taking into account the nature of the processing of shaped surfaces, is quite limited in modern literature. Constant processing modes when turning a surface with a complex curvilinear generatrix cannot ensure high process efficiency for the

following reasons: changing the kinematic geometric parameters of the tool; changing the parameters of the cut – width and thickness; changing the trajectory of the tool and the continuously changing direction of feed; variability of thermal processes in the processing zone.

Therefore, it is of interest to work on improving the efficiency of processing such surfaces directly with carbide cutters, as well as other tools in general.

Analysis of the choice of a carbide cutter in order to increase efficiency

Over the past decades, the volume of various types of tool materials for blade tools consumed by metalworking industries in technologically developed countries has changed a lot. Carbon and alloy tool steels are practically not used for blade tools. Consumption of high-speed steels has significantly decreased from 65...70% to 35...40%, while the volume of use of hard alloys has increased from 30% to 55%, and cutting ceramics and superhard tool materials from 1% to 10%.

Of hard alloys, the best indicators both in strength and wear resistance are materials made by powder metallurgy methods, which also allow forming a workpiece as close in shape as possible to the final shape of the cutting tool.

The share of using relatively inexpensive cermets (tungsten-free hard alloys) is significantly increasing, which in some cases are not inferior, and sometimes even superior in performance to traditional tungsten-containing hard alloys. In Japan, the share of the use of cermets reaches 40% of the volume of carbide tools. Undoubtedly, we should expect a significant increase in the use of cermets in the Russian industry.

A fundamentally new type of ultrafine-grained hard alloys with a unique bending strength commensurate with the strength of high-speed steels has appeared. The production of blanks of such hard alloys in the form of rods of various diameters leads to a tendency to manufacture the necessary end tools directly at the enterprises themselves when using multi-coordinate CNC grinding machines.

Carbide plates for turning cutters are one of the most convenient types of cutting tools. The fact is that the cutters are produced both with a one-piece design, when

the entire tool is one-piece and the cutting part is inextricably connected to everything else, and with removable parts, which is much more convenient in the process of work, when you can remove and replace one plate with another.

This is also convenient when replacing in case of breakage or wear. Plates for cutting cutters can be made of various materials and alloys, so that they can be several in a set for one type of tool, which is useful for interacting with different types of workpieces.

Carbide plates have the following advantages:

1. Low cost, compared to solid cutters;
2. The possibility of a quick change;
3. Reliably manifest themselves even in intensive modes of operation;
4. Possibility of plate changeover;
5. Control of cutting modes in order to increase productivity and reduce the cost of processing;
6. Greater unification of aggregates and tools.

Carbide plates for turning tools are classified according to the following parameters:

1. The type, or for which tools they are used, since cutting, grooving, undercutting, shaped, boring and other varieties require their own shape of the cutting profile, which is created according to the features that will have to be encountered in the work.

2. The material from which the products are made may have a different composition. Despite the fact that they all belong to the carbide type, the ratio of tungsten, titanium and other metals may still differ, depending on the required working conditions.

3. Dimensions – depending on the parts with which the work will be carried out, the plates may have different sizes. When processing relatively small workpieces with small diameters, a large cutter with a large plate may simply not

pass into it. For this purpose, identical in type and material, for different sizes, products for metal turning tools are created.

4. The value of the rear angle – this parameter is indicated in the brand of the product. The roughness of the treated surface depends on it, the higher it is, the smoother the surface becomes. For soft metals, plates with a large rear angle are used.

5. Accuracy class – there are five accuracy classes of these products, which provide different degrees of rigidity in terms of dimensional tolerances.

The marking displays the composition that is included in the products. Replaceable carbide plates for cutters are found with the markings T5K10 and T15K6. Using the example of T15K6, it can be understood that they belong to the products of the titanium tungsten group. The content of titanium carbide in it is 15%, cobalt – 6%.

For each type of these types of tools there is its own GOST, according to which plates with certain parameters fall:

1. GOST 19086-80 – this includes carbide materials for mechanical cutting and support type cutters, as well as chip breakers;
2. GOST 19042-80 – refers to replaceable polyhedral products;
3. GOST 25490-90 – carbide materials of types 61, 62, 01, 02. These can be revolver, passing and boring tools.

Figure 2 – Carbide plates.

Of the cutting ceramics, the most promising are ceramics hardened with filamentous crystals of silicon nitride and sialones.

Of superhard materials, it should be noted the appearance of polycrystalline diamond blade tools of a new type, manufactured using chemical vapor deposition technology (CVD-diamond). In the near future, we should expect the appearance on the market of a single-crystal diamond tool obtained using a similar technology, which will allow several times to reduce the prices of a single-crystal blade tool compared with a tool based on natural diamonds and diamonds obtained using traditional synthesis technologies.

In this analysis, it should be noted the prospects of using wear-resistant coatings on blade tools that significantly increase tool durability or processing performance, however, the creation of new types of coatings and the expansion of their use is an unambiguous global trend to improve the efficiency of cutting, including for shaped surfaces.

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